

Integration of strengthening of character education and higher order thinking skills in history learning

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to find integration packages for Strengthening Character Education (PPK) and Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in history learning at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta, which includes: (1) form of integration packaging for strengthening character education in history learning, (2) forms of integration packaging higher-order thinking skills in history learning, (3) constraints and solutions for integrating strengthening of character education and higher-order thinking skills in history learning. This research is qualitative research with a naturalistic research type. The subjects in this study were the principal, deputy headmaster of the curriculum section, history teacher, and students who were drawn using purposive sampling techniques. The results showed: (1) Integration of character education reinforcement was found in history learning, namely in the planning, implementation and evaluation stages of learning. Forms of integration packaging or containers for strengthening character education that can be seen in learning activities and attitude assessments that contain religious values, conscientious, disciplined, responsible, communicative, collaborating, confident, caring, critical thinking, nationalist and creative; (2) The packaging for integrating higher-order thinking skills in history learning is found, namely in assessment and questions as well as in learning planning. The assessment carried out is an assessment of attitudes, knowledge, and skills that are integrated with the questions by conducting KD analysis. The results of the analysis then the teacher chooses the KD that can be made about HOTS; and (3) Obstacles that are found that are technical in inserting character values in learning activities on historical subjects that are suggested to history teachers to always participate in the Subject Teachers' Deliberation (MGMP) which is felt by researchers to be very helpful for teachers to exchange information, and sharing about the obstacles encountered. For the constraints of making assessment instruments, advice to the Principal, Teachers, and Education Office to conduct socialization and training in making assessment instruments, the grid then starts making HOTS questions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is currently experiencing a crisis of national character values, in which people's actions are far from nation's character. Violence has become a common thing to solve any problem. One form of this violence is the imposition of policies that occur at almost every level of the organization such as policy making

between the central and regional governments. Besides that, other problems which run rampant are moral degradation such as student brawls, drug abuse, free sex as well as terrorism.

Another phenomenon that occurs is the globalization. Globalization is a process where individuals, groups, communities, and countries that interact with each other, are related, dependent and influence each other, crossing national borders [1]. Globalization itself has positive and negative impacts on life. One of the advantage of globalization is the emergence of a mega competitive society where people are pursuing excellence and quality which result is a dynamic, active and creative environment. Globalization also triggers global trends such as the ongoing digital revolution, changes in civilization and the increasingly firm phenomenon of the creative century. On the other side, the negative impact is the destruction of local culture both regionally and nationally.

Globalization has also some major effect in education, which is very complex. The influence given by globalization in education has the major impact on determining student's future. The key of success are strengthening students' adaptability toward changes through by growing national values of religiosity and local wisdom. Combining strong characters and adequate competence is the solution to answer the challenges of the 21st-century era. Education units are regarded as a strategic mean for national-character building because it provides systems, infrastructures, and support which are established throughout Indonesia.

Character is human behavior that is universal covering all human activities in the form of thoughts, attitudes, feelings, words, and action based on religious norms, law, manners, culture, and customs [2]. The concept of character is what gave rise to character education. Character education is a system of planting and habituating values basen on national culture which includes aspects of knowledge, attitudes, feelings, and actions, both towards God, oneself, society, and nation [3]. The problems above show that Indonesians are still lacking the awareness of character education. Community to support noble morals and ethics to be in line with national education goals and Presidential Regulation No. 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education is an urgent need. One of the character education goals is to build and equip the students as Indonesian golden generation to prepare for the future. Character education strengthening is not a new subject and a curriculum neither, but instead, it is a reinforcement or focus of the learning process as well as a spirit of education. Strengthening the roles needed in character education includes some main components such as principal, teachers, school committees, and the society.

There are two historical subjects in the 2013 curriculum for high school, namely Indonesian History and Specialized History. The Indonesian history subjects has main purpose for forming national character and identity. In history, its mandatory scope serves as learning to foster an attitude of nationalism and developing the student's character. On the other side, specialized history subject aims as a contextual and critical study, so that students are required to be able to develop critical and contextual attitudes [4]. History is the basis for the development of national identity which is one of the main assets in the development of the nation now and in the future [5]. Current technological advances have resulted in changes in all fields of life including education. Education is a strategic tool to improve character. One way to improve character is by inserting a load of character values into subjects. Historical subjects are considered capable of being loaded with character values. From these statements, it can be seen that history lessons can change the character of a nation and foster a level of students' thinking.

The current 2013 curriculum has undergone several revisions, one of which is the content and assessment standards. In the content standard, the main change is to stimulate the students to be able to think critically and analytically, based on international standards. It is achieved by reducing material that is not appropriate while deepening and expanding the suitable materials. Meanwhile, the assessment standard starts to adapt international standard models gradually. In the 2013 curriculum, the learning approach undertaken emphasizes the importances of scientific process through the stages of the learning process, which consists of: 1) observing; 2) ask questions; 3) gathering information, 4) reasoning or associating, and 5) communicating. Where the instrument for evaluating learning outcomes will focus more on higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) [6].

The improvement of the curriculum is certainly to improve students' higher-order thinking skills. One of the abilities that must be possessed in the 21st century is HOTS [7]. Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) are high-level thinking skills that consist of the ability to analyze, evaluate and create [8]. Based on the results of international studies of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), literacy achievement (reading literacy), mathematical literacy (mathematical literacy), and scientific literacy (scientific literacy) of Indonesian students is very low. Moreover, the 21st century's increasingly competitive capability demands four competencies, which are: Critical Thinking and Problem Solving, Creativity and Innovation, Communication and Collaboration. In this case, education as the bearer of the reformative and transformative roles must be able to prepare students to master these various skills. The need for graduates who are critical, creative and communicative and collaborative is the main graduate competency in the 2013 curriculum.

The Ministry of Education and Culture has inserted about 20% of HOTS (Higher Order Thinking Skills) questions in the National Examination (UN) in 2015-2016. Even to face the High School Exams (US) for the 2016-2017 academic year the Ministry of Education and Culture has compiled the HOTS question writing module. According to Pi'i [9], it shows that every teacher, including the history teacher, is required to assess learning outcomes by using HOTS questions to meet the demands of the KD which have a high level of cognitive thinking.

Higher Order Thinking Skills is a learning model that is needed in today's learning. Higher Order Thinking Skills are skills that train students to be able to solve problems in the future so that these skills must be possessed. To test students' thinking skills, assessments are designed in such a way that students answer questions through thinking processes that are operational verbs in Bloom's taxonomy [10]. Higher Order Thinking Skills are divided into four groups: problem-solving, decision making, critical thinking, and creative thinking [11].

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach to the type of naturalistic research. Design in naturalistic research is emergent, that is, this research cannot be determined in advance with certainty, because it is flexible [12]. The statement implies that this design did not put forward a hypothesis, but rather an analysis carried out from the beginning. Researchers used naturalistic research methods to be able to describe and analyze in-depth the integration of strengthening character education and higher-order thinking skills in learning history at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta. This research is natural in which researchers let the problems to arise naturally and then draw an interpretations that are supported by obtained data from the field.

Data collection techniques in this study are in the form of interviews, observation, and documentation. Sources of data in this study consisted of principals, vice-principals in the field of curriculum, history teachers, and students. The instruments in this study included in-depth interviews; documentation in the form of books; Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran (RPP) and syllabus; documents in the form of photographs; data gathered from observation from class activities as well as conditions in SMAN 1 Yogyakarta. The study was conducted from September to November 2019.

The data that has been collected then analyzed. Data analysis in this study uses the interactive analysis of Miles and Huberman models. According to Miles and Huberman [13] the analysis process includes data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and concluding. Then the analysis process starts from recapitulating all data, carried out data reduction including data simplification by selecting and sorting the required data. Furthermore, the reduction data is adjusted to the analysis design that has been designed which is then displayed. Each data reduction that has been adjusted is then verified with various field facts. After the data display has been verified, a conclusion is drawn.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Strengthening character education in learning

Siswoyo, et al [14], said education is a communication process which contains a transformation of knowledge, values, and skills in school and outside of school that lasts a lifetime (life long process). And then Berkowitz [15] defines character as a psychological trait that affects a person's ability and tendency to act based on moral values. Whereas according to Lickona [16], a character is not something that is carried from birth by individuals, but a habit that is regularly processed so that it becomes a personality that distinguishes each individual. Character is not something empty but character can be taught through family, school, and community environments that have positive values for life. From this character concept then emerged the concept of character education (character education).

A policy is certainly made based on mutual agreement, based on the phenomenon of everyday life and has a noble purpose for good and satisfying results, including character education. The purpose of character education is to build a strong, competitive, noble, moral, tolerant, cooperation, patriotic-spirited, dynamic, and science-oriented and science-oriented, an all-imbued nation with faith and devotion to God Almighty based on Pancasila (Narwanti, 2011) [17]. The purpose of strengthening character education has the meaning that education is not just about intellectuality but there is something more important that is prioritizing character education as the core or main soul.

In every policy that is carried out, there must be weaknesses and strengths. In the case of moral education and manners implementation, there are weaknesses in which the solution have been pursued through various character education innovations These innovations include: a) integrating character education into all subjects, b) integrating character education into the implementation of student coaching activities, c) carrying out character education through the management of all affairs in schools, involving all school members [18].

Of the three forms of innovation that are directly in contact with daily learning activities is the integration of character education in the learning process. Integration of character education in the learning process is carried out starting from the planning stage, implementation, and the evaluation of learning in all subjects [19].

Talking about strengthening character education will certainly touch on the value that would be instilled in students. Character values depend on what character will be formed later. Perpres No. 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education in Article 3 states 18 values that need to be applied in the implementation of strengthening character education, namely religious values, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard-working, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, love the motherland, appreciate achievement, communicative, love peace, love to read, care about the environment, care about social, and responsible.

From the 18 character values then simplified to 5 main character values. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture [20], the five main characteristics of the nation in question are Religious, Nationalist, Independent, Mutual Cooperation, and Integrity. The five main values interact and develop dynamically. Religious values as a reflection of faith and devotion to God Almighty are fully realized in the form of worship in accordance with their respective religions and beliefs and in the form of life between humans as groups, communities, and nations. In life as a society and nation, religious values are meant to underlie and merge in the main values of nationalism, independence, mutual cooperation, and integrity. Likewise, if nationalist main values are used as a starting point for the cultivation of character values, these values must be developed based on the values of faith and piety that grow with other values (Kemendikbud, [20]).

However, the five values can be adjusted to the school and local wisdom. The choice of character values can be adjusted to the situation and condition of the school. It aims to make students able to compete not only with hard skills but also soft skills which will help them adapt to the work environment and society.

3.2. Higher order thinking skills in learning

The 2013 curriculum which is currently in effect has undergone improvements to the content and assessment standards. The content standards are designed so that students can think critically and analytically according to international standards by reducing irrelevant material and deepening and expanding the material that is relevant to students. Whereas the assessment standard is done by adopting international standard assessment models gradually. Assessment of learning outcomes is more focused on higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) [6]. Higher Order Thinking Skills basically higher cognitive abilities [21].

The characteristics of HOTS are (1) measuring high-level thinking ability, minimizing aspects of memory or knowledge, (2) contextual problem-based, (3) interesting stimuli, and (4) non-routine. The characteristics of higher-order thinking include the ability to find, analyze, create new methods, reflect, predict, argue, and make the right decisions [6].

Dimensions of HOTS cognitive processes according to Anderson & Krathwohl (2001) [22] include creating, evaluating, and analyzing. Creating, namely creating ideas or verbs, verbs: construct, design, create, develop, write, formulate. Evaluating, i.e. making my own decisions, verbs: evaluating, evaluating, refuting, deciding, choosing, and supporting. Analyzing, namely specifying aspects/elements, verbs: comparing, checking, criticizing, and testing.

Whereas HOTS questions measure ability to: (1) transfer of one concept to another, (2) process and apply information, (3) look for links of different kinds of information, (4) use information to solve problems, and (5) critically examine ideas and information. The steps to compile HOTS questions include: (1) analysing Basic Competencies (KD) that can be made about HOTS questions, (2) compiling problem grids, (3) choosing interesting and contextual stimuli, (4) writing question items on the question card in accordance with the question grid, the question items are written to conform to the writing rules of the item, and (5) make a scoring guideline or answer key. (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2017) [6].

The steps to compile HOTS stimulus include (Batubara & Ajat, 2019) [23]: (1) choose the information that is related in a case, (2) stimulus should require the ability to interpret, look for relationships, analyze, conclude, or create, (3) choose contextual and interesting cases/problems (current) order learners are motivated to read, exceptions to the subject language, history may not be contextual, and (4) directly related to questions (subject matter). A problem can be categorized as a HOTS problem because in solving the problem [24]: (1) an understanding of the concept of reading diagrams and reading tables is needed, and looking at the relationship (looking for relations) information on the stimulus, (2) counting the number of internet users using comparisons, and (3) comparing internet users in Indonesia with users in Asia. The role of HOTS questions includes [25]: (1) preparing students 'competencies in the 21st century, (2) fostering love and caring for the progress of the region, (3) increasing students' learning motivation, and (4) improving the quality of questions. Teachers must be creative in honing students' higher-order thinking skills. The teacher must be able to make varied questions in the form of contextual cases according to the level of students' knowledge and experience

in daily life. Question words to hone the ability to think at a higher level, for example by using the words: why, how to, give reasons, in what ways, and how to act.

3.3. Integration of strengthening character education in history learning

The research process identified the efforts of the history teacher at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta in attempting to integrate character education in history learning well. The intended integration includes the loading of values of character reinforcement into the substance of historical subjects and the implementation of teaching and learning activities that facilitate the practice of values in every learning activity in the classroom and outside the classroom.

The integration of strengthening character education in the learning process is carried out starting from the planning stage, implementation to the evaluation of learning.

Planning Stage

In this planning stage, the teacher begins to carry out *Kompetensi Dasar* (KD) analysis to identify character values that can be substantially integrated into the relevant KD. The next step is to develop a syllabus by revising the syllabus that has been developed by adding the component (column) character value to the right of the component (column) Basic Competence. After that, the teacher revised the *Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran* (RPP) with several steps which included: the formulation of learning objectives revised/added learning objectives specifically formulated for a character; the approach/method used is changed and adjusted as using the principles of contextual learning approaches and active learning which are quite effective in developing the character of students. Then in the assessment section also carried out a revision that is by changing and/ or adding assessment techniques to determine the development of the character that is by observation, the evaluation between friends, and self-assessment. This value is stated qualitatively. Character values integrated into the planning stage are religious values, conscientious, disciplined, responsible, critical thinking, communicating, collaborating, and being creative.

Learning Implementation Stage

At this stage, the learning activities consist of introduction, core, and closing. The results of direct field observations made that the teacher has integrates character values in learning activities. The teacher uses a scientific approach to the group learning model and discovery learning and uses the method of discussion and experimentation. The implementation is also a place for integration of character education. The integrated character values are religious, conscientious, responsible, caring, cooperative, confident, communicative, critical, nationalist and creative.

Learning Evaluation Stage

Learning history assessments include cognitive, skill and affective assessments. The teacher has understood the principles of assessment that are correct and by established assessment standards namely, Educational Assessment Standards established by the Ministry of Education and Culture No. 23 of 2016. In assessing the character of students, the teacher has made an assessment instrument that is equipped with an assessment rubric to avoid subjective assessment, namely in form of observation assessment instruments (observation sheets) and attitude scale assessment instruments. The attitude assessment component can be used as a place of integration of character values. Integrated values are honesty, discipline, responsibility, confidence, nationalism and caring.

From the learning process that includes these three stages, it is still found obstacles that are experienced by the teacher, namely at the stage of implementation of learning and evaluation of learning. At the learning stage, the lack of hours in history subjects does not correspond to the amount of material that will be given to students. So the teacher has a little difficulty in facilitating the internalization of character values in learning. Beside that, another obstacle found in the learning evaluation stage is that the teacher has too much burden on the school administration so that the teacher can only make an attitude assessment instrument.

3.4. Integration of higher order thinking skills in history learning

Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) include critical, logical, reflective, metacognitive, and creative thinking. In the refinement of the 2013 curriculum, the content and assessment standards have been designed to be adjusted by gradually adapting international standard models.

The assessment conducted by the history teacher at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta during the study was to use techniques/methods of performance appraisal, paper or pencil test or project evaluation, project appraisal, appraisal through a collection of students' work/works (portfolio), and self-assessment.

The assessment of history subjects in the 2013 Curriculum was carried out through an assessment of attitudes, knowledge, and skills. The assessment of knowledge is obtained by the teacher from the activities of

remembering, reflecting, deduction, and induction (research). Knowledge assessment conducted by history teachers at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta is done through written tests in the form of multiple-choice tests, content, and descriptions conducted during daily tests, midterm and end of the semester and in the form of quizzes to find out how far students could absorb the provided material. Furthermore, teachers also use oral form tests, so that students are not afraid to express their answers, orally. Besides that the teacher also assesses students through assignments, both individual and group assignments.

The assessment of skills is inseparable from the assessment of knowledge and attitudes. The skills assessment conducted by the history teacher is that the teacher conducts a practice/performance, project and portfolio assessment that is adjusted to the competency characteristics of historical subjects which will be measured in the form of an assessment scale that is completed with a rubric.

Higher Order Thinking Skills can be integrated in addition to the assessment and can also be integrated with the questions. By Permendikbud No. 37 of 2018 concerning KI-KD, how to do KD analysis. The results of the analysis then the teacher chooses the KD that can be made about HOTS questions which contain KD tables that can be made about HOTS questions. Examples of KD that can be analyzed into HOTS problems can be seen in the Table 1.

Table 1. KD analysis table

No	KD	Cognitive Level
Class X Semester 1		
3.1	Analyzing Human Life in time and space	L3/C4
3.2	Analyzing Human Life in change and sustainability	L3/C4
3.3	Analyzing the Interrelationship of Historical Events About humans in the past for present life	L3/C4
3.4	Analyze History as science, events, stories and art	L3/C4
3.5	Analyzing diachronic and synchronous thinking in historical work	L3/C4
3.6	Evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of various forms / types of historical sources (artifacts, fossils, textual, non-contextual, material, visual, audiovisual, oral traditions)	L3/C5

The integration of HOTS conducted by teachers is also found in the preparation of learning plans that can be seen from the learning objectives that contain cognitive levels (analyze, evaluate and create), in learning materials, there are universal problems, the use of media used by teachers can encourage students to think critically, the choice of varied methods coupled with the activity of analyzing, as well as in evaluating the questions given to students there is a stimulus that is open to the cognitive realm (analyze, evaluate and create). The obstacle when doing the research was found when choosing a material that is reduced and expanded to be designed in order students can think critically and analytically according to international standards. The problem is the ever-changing demands forces the teachers to be up-to-date with the current development.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion the following conclusions can be drawn. First, in integrating the strengthening of character education in learning it was found that in SMAN 1 Yogyakarta had implemented character values that were included in each subject, including history subjects. History teachers have implemented internalization of character values through learning activities at the planning, implementation and evaluation stages of learning. Integrated character values are religious values, conscientious, disciplined, responsible, communicative, collaborating, confident, caring, critical thinking, nationalist and creative. But indeed there are still some obstacles that are the differences in character and background of each student to be less than the maximum in integrating the values of character education.

Secondly, the integration of HOTS into the history learning by the teacher has been done and applied according to what already exists in the HOTS preparation module. It has also been adjusted to the existing assessment standards in Permendikbud. However, in the field, several obstacles were found that made history teachers less optimal in developing assessment and question instruments based on HOTS that is when choosing the materials that is reduced and expanded to be used as a design so that students are able to think critically and analytically according to international standards. The ever-changing demands make teachers must always follow the uptodate development.

The suggestions as an alternative way to overcome the problems experienced at SMAN 1 Yogyakarta are as follows. To overcome technical obstacles in adding character values in learning activities in historical subjects, it is suggested to the History Teacher to always participate in MGMP activities. The researchers suggested so since, the MGMP is very helpful for teachers to exchange information and share the problem they face. For the constraints of making assessment instruments, advice to the Principal, Teachers, and Education Office to conduct socialization and training in making assessment instruments, grids and just start making HOTS questions.

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